

ANALYSIS OF CYBER SAFETY AWARENESS

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ABSTRACT

Objectives :

The Web has made another specialized apparatus, especially for youngsters whose utilization of electronic correspondence is detonating around the world. While there are many advantages of electronic-based correspondence, the Web is simultaneously a potential site for manhandle and exploitation. This research intends to examine the level of ethical and security awareness among students of Ahmedabad University.

Methods :

A questionnaire based survey method was followed to examine level of awareness of cyber security amongst students. The findings of this study can be useful for the college management to understand the mentality of the students while setting up policies and regulations to reduce the instances of cyber crimes in the student community.

Results :

The findings of this study reveals that there is very low level of awareness among the students surveyed. Only 30 percent of the students have attended any seminar or lecture related to cyber security.

Keywords: Cyber Security, Passwords, Awareness, Survey

INTRODUCTION

Internet and Communication Technology has opened wide doors for the people of all ages, including student community to contribute and accumulate information.

People get connected through emails, IRCs, social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter etc, blogs etc. Internet has made it possible for users to avail online banking, shopping as well as e-library facilities. Use of the Internet has become more central in our daily life.

One of the biggest risks for an organization's information security is often not a weakness in the technology control environment. Or maybe it is the action or inaction by workers and users that can prompt security occurrences - for example, through disclosure of personal information that could be used in a social engineering attack, not reporting observed unusual activity, accessing sensitive information carelessly, and so on. So , it is essential for students of this generation to have knowledge of cyber security.

A recent study by ASSOCHAM and PwC revealed 46% complaints of cyber crime are related to credit debit card fraud followed by Facebook (39%) related complaints which include morphed pictures, cyber stalking, and bullying. Study also stated that there will be rise of 65% in mobile frauds in India due to increasing trend of mobile wallets.

College students are more privileged than the school students when it comes to internet usage as the higher educational institutes may offer emails for the students. Thus, they are more exposed to cyber world. They may be easy victim of cyber crime because of limited knowledge of cyber security.

Under such desperate situation, other than handling the cybercrimes, another issue that should be centered around higher need is making them aware & beware of "cyber crimes and security" among the internet users. Along these lines the present review centers in discovering the responses to disturbing inquiries related to awareness of cyber security.

METHODOLOGY

Design of Survey

- Literature review was performed to identify parameters which reflect the Cyber Security awareness.
- A questionnaire based on such fundamentals of Cyber security was designed to record the response of the participants from Ahmedabad University.
- Efforts were taken to limit the number of questions in the questionnaire and the resulting number of questions was 15.

Participants

The Cyber Safety Awareness Survey was completed by 352 students of Ahmedabad University. The survey was conducted using online mechanism and was circulated to all students of Ahmedabad University.

EXPOSURE TO INTERNET

FREQUENCY OF EXPOSURE

TYPICAL ACTIVITIES

MODE OF ACCESS

Smart Phone is the most common amongst students to access internet, followed by Laptop.

A few of respondents uses tablet and personal computer to access internet.

KNOWLEDGE OF CYBER SECURITY

Q. Were you ever taught about cyber security in your school/college?

A question was asked in the survey to know whether the respondents were taught about cyber security in their respective school/college or not. It is seen that majority of students have not received any type of knowledge of the cyber security from their school/college.

Q. Have you ever attended any seminar/lecture on cyber security?

In the response to the question if the respondent have ever attended any seminar/lecture focused on cyber security **70%** replied in negative.

ONLINE TRANSACTIONS

Around 88% students replied that have performed online transactions whereas 12.5% respondents replied in negative.

PASSWORD HYGIENE

Q. How often do you change PIN of your debit/credit cards?

In the response to the question that how often do respondent changes PIN of his debit/credit cards around 55% replied that they have never changed their PIN, while only **3.4%** students changes their PIN every few weeks.

Q. How often do you change your password of social media platform accounts?

From above graph, It can be seen that majority of students change their password once a year and another major part of students have never changed their passwords of social media accounts.

Quick Tips:

- ⌘ **Passwords should be treated like tooth-brush.**
Change them early and often. Don't share them with anyone and don't leave them lying around.
- ⌘ **Use a password manager.**
- ⌘ **The longer the password, the better.**
Make passwords that are a combination of 4 or more different words.

FEAR OF INTERNET

A question was asked to respondents to know what was their biggest fear while using internet. Theft of personal information, Fraud, and theft of money and Account hijacking are the top most situations that students fear of.

SECURITY THREATS

PUBLIC WIFI

USAGE OF ANTI VIRUS/ANTI MALWARE ON MOBILE

⌘ **200+ Malware families are identified alone on “Android” platform.**

⌘ **82% of travellers are connecting their phones with a public WiFi to access the web, exposing them to vulnerabilities.**

- Kaspersky Labs

⌘ Quick Tips :

- **Don't shop online when using public Wi-Fi.**
- **Do turn off automatic connectivity.**
- **Don't access personal bank accounts, or sensitive**

The weakest link in the security chain is the human element

-Kevin Mitnick

AWARENESS OF CYBER LAWS

A question “Are you aware of the Indian Cyber Law(Information Technology Act - 2000)?” was asked to respondents with three options. Majority of students replied in “No” or “Heard about it” (38%, 39%).

It can be seen that level of awareness of cyber law is negligible among students.

Q. One of your friend is being harassed by someone on “Whatsapp”, What will you suggest in this situation?

This question was asked to find how student will deal if his/her friend is a victim of cyber crime. 85% of students replied that they would suggest their friend to lodge a complaint at nearest Cyber Cell It shows a good knowledge of incident response, while the rest part replied with non-favourable choices like “suggesting victim to change mobile number” and “asking friend to be silent”.

A question “Have you ever been cyber bullied?” was asked to identify number of students who had been victim of cyber crime. Almost all respondents were on safe side but about 10% of students have been recently victimised in cyberbullying.

CONCLUSION

The study proves that students in Ahmedabad University are not thoroughly aware of cybercrimes and cyber security. The convergence of smart phones and internet are on stride and popular. This means, there is more scope for cybercrimes. The absence of awareness is very dangerous for their smartphones, laptops and other digital resources. Lack of updating passwords of accounts in timely manner may lead to various financial frauds.

During research it is observed that majority of students are using public WiFi for performing transactions without understanding threats related to it. Lack of cyber security awareness not only affects individual resources but may also create great problem for institutes digital infrastructure.

We feel that cyber security awareness training will help students to improve their fundamentals regarding cyber threats.

CYBERSECURITY IS A
SHARED RESPONSIBILITY,
AND IT BOILS DOWN TO
THIS: IN CYBERSECURITY,
THE MORE SYSTEMS
WE SECURE, THE MORE
SECURE WE ALL ARE.

- Jeh Johnson

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